

ISic3447

Funerary inscription of Caius Sextius

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

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Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2014.10.30 Metcalfe

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Menae

Place of origin (modern)

near Mineo

Provenance

Monte Catalfaro

Coordinates

37.280623, 14.717130

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Mineo, Museo Civico Corrado
Tamburino Merlini, inventory 5194

Physical Description

An intact slab of limestone

Dimensions

Height 53 cm

Width 54 cm

Depth 6 cm

Layout

Latin text over two lines, with the second line centred

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Lines 1-2: 90-100 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. C (ai) · Sexti

2. sal (ve)

Apparatus

Translation

Gaius Sextius, farewell!

Commentary

The text employs the vocative and salutation formula which is found in several of the Greek epitaphs from Mineo, including the text on the reverse of this stone (ISic3448)

Digital identifiers:

TM 644925
EDCS 70900746

Bibliography

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- Cordano, F. 2014. Materiale vecchio e nuovo dalla Sicilia orientale. In Alfieri Tonini, T., Struffolino, S.(eds.), *Dinamiche culturali ed etniche nella Sicilia orientale dall'età classica all'epoca ellenistica*. Trento. pp. 105-111. At 107-108 no.6

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Photo M. Metcalfe